

The City or the Country

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Definition

Country is defined as extended expanse of land. It is also the land where a person is born and live. On the other hand, city is a place where people reside and work. City is bigger than a town and is part of the country. For example, Canada is a country and Toronto is its city. When it comes to making a decision to live in a city or country, people have very differing views. Many people are of the opinion that living in a country is like a beautiful dream, watching beautiful sights and listening to natural music and etc. It can be said that country life is better, but this statement is challenged by many theorists.

Similarities and differences

There are various similarities between country living and city living. The first one is convince. What is more convenient to a person. Some people argue that convince is only found in city living. However, this is not always the case and convince between country and city life are depicted in a very different way. For instance, in the city, several people are interested in purchasing serviced food. Also, it is easier to get a meal in a very short span of time, but it's very rare that people living in a city can cook well. On the other hand, people in the county have the habit of cooking , so they cook better that the city persons. Also, they save a substantial amount along with enjoying the feast (Blueloralie,2010)

Also, people form various schools of thought and background in the city thinks that they possess better job opportunities, better schooling facilities and many other opportunities than country people. On the other hand, people in the city have to work very hard to earn money and feel more pressure, although, in many other areas, they have more advantages the people living in the country. Whereas, living in a country is cheaper, but they don't have all the services like

the people in the city have. Also, the people in the country don't have to pay very high bills since they have fewer services and facilities. Therefore, people living in both country and city have convinces, but in different forms (Nipolak, 2013).

The second similarity is related to life conditions. Many old age people believe that country life is like poems, where people are listening to interesting music, having a sight of animals. However, on the other hand, young people are of the view that people living in a country have very boring and sad life. Also, they are of the view that people in country enjoy relaxed life. Soothing and fresh air to breathe, less traffic and noise. Whereas, in the city, people maintain young by having good doctors, state of the art hospitals and healthy systems.

Characteristics of people living in the country and city are the third similarity between theses two. It is said people living in a country are more friendly than compared to the people living in the city. Also, city people are also friendly but don't have time to talk and hangout. Also, time is equivalent to money for city living people (Essayforum.com, 2013).

There are also many other similarities between the city and country living. Both of them grow and change very quickly; also they have many other similar features, as well. These include restaurants, hospitals shopping centers, police station and etc. Both of them are filled with history and knowledge and possess hard working people, who are trying to live and to take care of.

Therefore, in the light of the information depicted above it can be said that both city living or country living are not better from each other. Both of them have various similarities and differences that give them edge over one another. Everything depends on the person choice, thoughts and hobbies.

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